

ISic0416

I.Sicily inscription 0416

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 251; 50782

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]UPIL[---]
2. [---]quod si [quis][---]
3. [---]inferat a[---]
4. [---] CC milia [sibietsuisetlibertisliber]
5. [---]tabusqu[e][---]

Apparatus

text of CIL

CIL: The final letter following 'a' is either 'n', 'p' or 'i', but it cannot be 'e'.

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175781

EDR 081524

EDCS 21900479

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7136 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650767>)

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0342f

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 183 no.63 fig.68-68a

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0416. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4335584>